

D5.1 Communication materials

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Document overview

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Executive Summary

ALMASI's overall objective is to provide the research community with a globally aligned, nonprofit, high-quality, and sustainable scholarly communication ecosystem capable of implementing Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing as a standard quality publication practice. The specific needs of scholarly communities across the diversity of disciplines and global regions will be taken into account. Special attention will be paid to multilingual communication (English, Spanish, French, Portuguese).

ALMASI covers three regions with a wide variety of countries and cultures. One of the major communication challenges of ALMASI will lay in translating key outputs into four languages: English, French, Spanish, and Portuguese. This choice is based on their widespread use in the regions under investigation and the demand in the target communities. Collaborative work and shared linguistic skills among the partners will be an asset, as output materials will not only be translated but also adapted.

The ALMASI project's website, visual identity, Communications kit, and social media channels, as presented in this deliverable, provide an overview of the project's identity and its external channels and means of communication.

Information and dissemination work will follow the visual guidelines outlined here. This document will be supported by Deliverable 5.3, which will outline how the project will use the elements described below in the project communication, dissemination, and engagement activities.

1. Visual identity

A visual identity was realised with artwork that was free to use, as well as an original logo and other resources. This will help our audiences to easily identify ALMASI and contribute to the project's visibility by providing a clear identity from the start of the project.

All communication and dissemination tools (project website, social media, etc.), materials (leaflets, presentations, etc.), and deliverables will incorporate this visual identity.

Project partners are asked to create their materials using the logos, colours, and templates from the visual identity guide.

New materials will be developed throughout the project.

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a. The ALMASI logo

To create the logo, specific instructions were given to the graphic designer:

- Use a design similar to the DIAMAS project using the shape of a diamond
- Use 3 colours to represent the 3 regions of the project
- Simple and lightweight design, easy to use and to adapt to various formats

b. Font

The **Barlow** font was chosen as a modern, easy-to-read font.

typography

BARLOW

<p>ABCDEFGHIJKLM NOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890!@#€\$ %^&*()_+}{:"?><.,/';][=-\ </p>	<p>ABCDEFGHIJKLM NOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890!@#€\$ %^&*()_+}{:"?><.,/';][=-\ </p>	<p>ABCDEFGHIJKLM NOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890!@#€\$ %^&*()_+}{:"?><.,/';][=-\ </p>
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c. Templates

A set of templates has been developed to ensure uniformity when communicating about the project.

The ALMASI PowerPoint template was created before the kick-off meeting, and participants were invited to use it.

d. Roll-up banner

Presented during the kick-off and official launch meeting, a roll-up banner was created and set up on stage to display the ALMASI visual identity. It contains the project logo with a tagline as well as the partners' logos.

2. The website

The ALMASI website is under development and will be available at <https://almasiproject.org> in English, French, Spanish, and Portuguese.

The website design was presented at the kick-off meeting in January 2025. It will represent the central digital hub for online communication activities of the project and engagement. It encompasses mainly information on ALMASI's partners, work packages' descriptions and activities, future results and outputs, as well as news and events.

This website is hosted and developed by a CNRS unit (INIST CNRS). It is a WordPress website on servers located in France and administered by INIST CNRS on behalf of the consortium.

The website structure will be adapted and reorganised with new categories and content to reflect the progress of the project, provide insights, and promote outcomes. All partners will be involved and encouraged to provide content.

Both the website and the outputs of the project will be published with accessibility criteria in mind. The website will be tested for accessibility with a tool such as the ANDI tool: <https://www.ssa.gov/accessibility/andi/help/install.html#install>.

Below you will find the contact details of all the organisations making up the ALMASI consortium.

3. Social media channels

ALMASI has selected different social media channels to address our different stakeholder groups and different communities in the three project regions. They allow the project to reach a broader audience than through more traditional dissemination

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activities. The project considers the use of an aggregator to distribute content automatically from one network to another.

The kick-off meeting discussed which social media to use, including whether or not to use X (Twitter), and if not, what other channel to select. The consortium decided to use Bluesky instead of X because of its better alignment with the project's overall values. It was also decided to create a LinkedIn page.

The Bluesky account and LinkedIn page have been set up and will be officially activated and announced with the launch of the website. A Facebook account has been set up to reach out to communities in Latin America and Africa, which have a strong presence on this medium.

The main goals of ALMASI's social media are to promote:

1. The different activities and news of the project
2. Events and publications
3. Nonprofit OA publishing solutions
4. Engage with ALMASI community members

a. LinkedIn page

LinkedIn page: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/almasi-project>

As LinkedIn is a professional network, most of ALMASI's members and stakeholder groups are connected on this platform. This page will mainly be used for:

- Publishing ALMASI's news and new blog posts
- Guiding users to the ALMASI's website
- Connecting with other institutions and stakeholders

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b. Bluesky

Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/almasiproject.bsky.social>

Bluesky is a decentralised, open social network that gives users more control over their data and content compared to other platforms. It has gained momentum recently, as many users have left X, but its audience is still smaller. ALMASI will trial BlueSky instead of X at the start of the project and assess whether it is worth maintaining long-term.

c. Facebook

Facebook page:

<https://www.facebook.com/people/Almasi-Project/61572808335305/>

ALMASI will use Facebook to raise awareness, promote its activities, and engage a wider audience. This platform was chosen because it has a strong presence in Latin America and Africa, key regions for the project. Being present on Facebook also allows ALMASI to connect with existing partner communities.

4. Press release

An initial press release was issued in English to announce the launch of ALMASI in February 2025 and will be available in the other three languages later on. This was the opportunity to present the ALMASI partners and the project's specific objectives.